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PROSPECTS OF ORGANIZING DISTANCE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the development of the global Internet system, the role of telecommunication technologies in the educational process of higher education and the prospects of distance education are highlighted in the article. The nature of the information society and information systems of education, the importance of distance education and distance learning in the information society is based. It is emphasized that during the COVID-19 pandemic, all branches of the education system around the world have been transferred to the distance education system, and the need to implement distance education in the form of separate education in Uzbekistan is based on this.

Key words: *information and communication, telecommunication, traditional education, Internet, modern teaching, distance education*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, a new era of development in human civilization has begun - the era of the information society. It is characterized by the rapid development of information and telecommunications, the rapid spread of information technologies, the globalization of society development processes, the formation of the international communication environment, education, communication and production, and the development of the infosphere. The organizational and technological basis of the information society is the global information network - Internet [1].

The rapid development of telecommunications is creating unconventional new and convenient opportunities in various spheres of society's life, such as politics, economy, education, culture, household service, and security. The new conditions of the development of the society make it a task to train new specialists using modern teaching technologies that meet the requirements of the information society [2].

The development of the global Internet system has opened up new prospects for evolutionary improvement in the world education system. Today, traditional teaching methods are being supplemented by new teaching methods based on the Internet, electronic computer sets and telecommunication environment. In addition to performing a number of new functions, tele-education and distance education based on Internet technology require the implementation of specific principles such as the principle of mutually distributed cooperation, integration, access to the international Internet network [3].

RESEARCH METHODS

In the research process, the analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test and foresight methods were used.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The current era requires a person to receive lifelong education, that is, to improve his professional knowledge and skills regularly throughout his life, which is certainly carried out on the basis of the development of the electronic-computer network and Internet technologies [4].

The development as a result of consistent policies in the economic and social spheres in our republic requires the introduction of new forms of education in the educational system. Therefore, organization of the educational system at a high quality level based on information and communication technologies is one of the urgent problems of today. The experience of developed countries shows that the economic, social and political status of each country in the world is ensured by its intellectual wealth, which is becoming the main factor in economic growth [5,6].

The new conditions of the development of the society make it a task to train specialists using modern teaching technologies that meet the requirements of the information society. Wide and rapid penetration of information technologies into various aspects of our life is creating the basis for the formation of an information society. Concepts such as "Electronic education", "Electronic government", "Electronic management", "Distance education", "Open education", "Information economy" have entered our lives. The organizational and technological basis of the information society is the global information network - the Internet. One such technology is distance learning technology. Today, there are different attitudes towards distance learning in different fields. For example, it is most widely used today to replace traditional training in the corporate sector and to study individual courses in the education sector. In addition, this form of training is becoming more and more popular in the fields of finance and information technology, in the retraining of

government employees, in medicine, in the non-profit sector, in industry, in trade and in other fields [7,8].

Distance education The worldwide spread of the COVID-19 pandemic and the implementation of strict quarantine measures required the introduction of distance education in the education system of all countries. Including distance learning in all areas of the education system in Uzbekistan. During the quarantine, training sessions were organized on the basis of special programs on television for secondary education, and Moodle was launched in higher education, and now the XEMIS platform, which includes administrative management, financial management, educational process and scientific activities of higher education, was launched. Monitoring of training and student knowledge was established through Zoom software systems and conference communication. The rapid establishment of distance learning in higher education due to the pandemic has shown that students and most professors are not ready for distance learning. It was especially difficult for professors over the age of 60 to quickly learn Moodle and Zoom programs [9].

In distance learning, students become the most active participants in the learning process, and Internet resources play an important role in this. It is necessary for students to clearly understand and understand the educational goal in the distance education system, and to understand the content of the problem on each subject and to have an independent scientific and creative approach to its solution. Also, in such a study system, the demand for the student's learning ability changes, the student must not only read, write, or perform practical calculations on a specific topic, i.e., the materials that the teacher has passed during the training, but must be able to distinguish, collect and creatively master the necessary from millions of educational resources on the global network of the Internet. will be [10].

Before putting each innovation into practice, special attention is paid to the study of advanced foreign experiences. When studying the educational system of developed countries, educational institutions in them organize and coordinate the educational process based on the requirements of the labor market and the demands of employers. A graduate of an educational institution requires not only professional professionalism, but also the ability to use information technology at a high level. This process, of course, implies self-development of future specialists with new professional knowledge and acquisition in a short period of time. That is, distance learning develops the skills of finding the necessary information from a huge database, analyzing it, bringing it into a known system, developing thoughts and ideas, designing, and expanding the mind and thinking.

CONCLUSION

It should be emphasized that distance education is a mandatory necessity of today's pandemic conditions all over the world, but prioritizing the independent form of education, the internal capabilities of educational institutions, material and technical bases, the age of the students and the work. A number of factors such as the need to receive education without separation, the distance of the students from the educational institutions of their choice, it can be seen that the developed countries have acquired their own unique experiences in this regard, following certain historical paths. Distance education technologies in developed countries are based on the basic principles of traditional education and widely use innovative technologies.

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